

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

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REPORT TO
THE FORD FOUNDATION
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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THE YEAR 1974-75

In a February 14, 1973, article, Library Journal commended "the impact the Ford Foundation-backed Council on Library Resources has had and continues to have on librarianship."

That statement is even more appropriate today, for perhaps at no time in its 19 years of assisting the library world has the Council had as much impact on libraries as in the past 12 months. The Library Journal's 1973 recognition of the Council referred to many activities then still in the seedling stage of growth. Now, at the close of the fiscal year, a number of these seedlings are approaching maturity. For example:

- A degree of order is being brought to the complicated matter of the bibliographic organization of periodicals by way of the Conversion of Serials (CONSER) Project.
- Formalized cooperation involving such institutions as the Library of Congress, the National Science Foundation, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, and the Council on Library Resources is enhancing the prospects for achieving national bibliographic control, a concept the Council has worked toward for many years.
- The Council's efforts to encourage the development of librarians' special skills are showing results that measure up well to original expectations.
- Cataloging in Publication at the Library of Congress, a project funded jointly with the National Endowment for the Humanities, has succeeded beyond the hopes of its most enthusiastic supporters. Now the Council and the Endowment are again cooperating in providing funds for another important project at the Library of Congress.

The list could go on for many pages and in a sense does, in the following sections which describe in detail the Council's activities

during the year just ended. The 1974-75 year was the busiest one in CLR's history, with grants for fellowships and 34 new programs amounting to \$3,002,004. In addition, 25 projects funded in previous years were active, and 25 projects were completed.

AUTOMATION, NETWORKS, STANDARDIZATION, AND NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES

Approximately 40 percent of the Council's program funds are allocated to activities, including those in automation and networking, that will lead to the development of national library services. The size of that percentage reflects not only the costs involved in making computers work for libraries, but also the essential nature of this activity in attaining the goal of providing the most efficient and economical library service to users.

The goal can be achieved only if we can reduce to a practical minimum the number of technical activities repeated in library after library, with great expense to each. The Council believes that the best way to accomplish this is through national library services -- designated agencies, whether governmental or private, that can perform these activities either cooperatively or from a single central source. Of these functions cataloging is perhaps the most costly and time consuming. It is the first such activity that should be thus considered, for it is basic to library operations. Cataloging, in library terms, is the dual process of uniquely identifying each publication (descriptive cataloging), and categorizing it by contents (subject analysis). It makes possible the creation of a "record" for each publication, resulting in the bibliographic control that provides the librarian with an inventory of the collection and the user with the essential tool in locating the information he seeks.

In 1974-75, with the strong support of the Council, many of the individual pieces of the national library puzzle began to fit together. The Council -- via management, coordinating, counseling, staffing, and funding roles -- is providing the impetus its founders

foresaw a score of years ago in citing the need for an independent body, free to attack the various problems of libraries through research, development, coordination of effort, and other appropriate means.

Ten new grants totalling \$1,511,538 were made by the Council in this broad category in 1974-75, representing nearly a third of the new grants made and about half of its new dollar commitment. Three holdover programs remained active, and eight others were completed.

National Bibliographic Control

A year ago at a three-day meeting jointly sponsored by the Council and the National Science Foundation (NSF), national bibliographic control was defined as "those principles and processes by which bibliographic items [recorded information in various media] are identified to the basic level required for management of and intellectual access to information of all types." It was the further consensus of the participants -- 45 leaders from the fields of librarianship, abstracting and indexing, publishing, information dissemination, and standardization -- that a national bibliographic system is needed and will be built, but gradually and at least in part from "programs of action which come out of this meeting."

In February 1975, CLR and NSF, joined by the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), announced the establishment of an Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control. Its mission: to advise the three sponsoring agencies on how best to coordinate their programs and to recommend priorities for action in this important area. Implementation of the Advisory Group's decisions is handled by Council staff members in the Council's offices. Now in existence and moving

forward are Working Parties on Formats for Journal Articles and Technical Reports, on Bibliographic Name Authority Files, and for a Standard Format for Reporting Serials Holdings. This last is actually Subcommittee 40 of Standards Committee Z-39 of the American National Standards Institute.

Conversion of Serials (CONSER)

Another important step in achieving bibliographic control is the CLR-managed CONSER Project, now in its second year and one of the most widely discussed programs in the library world today. The Council has allocated more than a quarter of a million dollars and two full-time professional staff members to managing and coordinating this effort to build a composite national data base of serials. A December 1974 contract with the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) for use of its computer facilities over the next two years and an agreement with the University of Minnesota, which willingly made its serials file available as the initial data base, were major steps taken in this fiscal year.

The authenticated file produced by CONSER will be available to the library community through the distribution services of the Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada, two of the institutions contributing their serials records on-line to the cooperative base. Other participants in the CONSER Project are National Library of Medicine, National Agricultural Library, Boston Theological Institute, Cornell University for FAUL (Five Associated University Libraries), Florida Union List of Serials Project, New York State Library, State University of New York, University of California, University of Minnesota, and Yale University.

CONSER has been further enriched by a CLR matching grant with the National Endowment for the Humanities to the Library of Congress, for the purpose of hastening the completion of the serials data base in the humanities. The National Science Foundation is also assisting with a grant for serials in science and technology.

It had originally been expected that the CONSER Project would be completed by late 1976. However, because of OCLC's inability to meet its promised schedule for loading the initial file, it now appears that the work will not be entirely accomplished before 1977.

Library of Congress

The Library of Congress (LC), recipient of more than \$2 million in Council grants over the years, is the key institution through which CLR cooperates in activities leading toward bibliographic control. This year the Council allocated another quarter of a million dollars (including the NEH grant cited above) for new projects in this area. Three activities now going forward at LC will do much to achieve the desired goal.

1. Certification of Converted LC Records. Because the scope of LC's MARC (Machine Readable Cataloging) coverage for book-form material is still limited, many libraries throughout the country are creating their own machine-readable records, basing many of them on LC cataloging copy derived from cards, proof sheets, and entries in the National Union Catalog. The Council grant will enable the Library to accept from authorized participants these locally generated records in machine-readable form, remove the duplicates, compare the records with the Official Catalog, update them for consistency when required, and

redistribute them through the MARC Distribution Service. Participants in the COMARC (Cooperative MARC) project are selected on the basis of the completeness of the data content of their records and their adherence to MARC encoding. They will receive the certified records at no cost during the period of the project; other libraries will be able to purchase the records at nominal cost through the MARC Distribution Service. The project should go far in providing consistency and a degree of standardization to locally created records, thus making it possible for them to be used by others.

2. Requirements Study. The Library of Congress has for some time been involved with the design and implementation of a Core Bibliographic System, which takes into account the services needed by outside libraries as well as the technical processing requirements for the Library itself. The CLR grant funds a consultant who, together with LC staff, will define the hardware and communications requirements for the system.

3. National Union Catalog Reporting Format. Since the initiation of the MARC Distribution Service, there have been discussions concerning the possibility of determining and identifying the minimum number of MARC data elements required uniquely to identify a publication. Several studies have been conducted and the conclusions have always been the same, i.e., that for the purpose of distributing and exchanging machine-readable cataloging records which are to satisfy a multitude of users and uses, no such subset of data from the current LC MARC data can be defined. However, for the specific purpose of reporting titles in machine-readable form to the National Union Catalog, it would be possible to define a less complete record than the present MARC record. This would make the information on holdings available to users in a

more timely fashion than at present. The Council grant will make this possible.

Standardization

Webster defines the word standard as "something established by authority, custom, or general consent as a model, example, or criterion; something set up or established by authority as a rule for the measure of quantity, weight, extent, value, or quality." In the context of the Council's work in national and international bibliographic control, standardization means the development and adoption of common codes, definitions, rules, and procedures, which will permit a common understanding of the format, control elements, and intellectual content of bibliographic records. If it is to be possible for libraries to exchange information about their holdings, or to share the task of constructing data bases, or to work together in consortia and networks, there must be absolute agreement on the conventions that govern library processes. This becomes even more essential when international exchange of information is involved, and an absolute requirement where automation is a factor.

The American National Standards Institute (ANSI) is responsible for setting voluntary national standards in many fields. Its Committee Z-39, which is directly responsible for standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing practices, has since 1966 received its support from the Council and the National Science Foundation; this year a new CLR grant of \$14,000 was authorized for the purpose. ANSI is the U.S. member of the International Standards Organization (ISO), which works internationally in much the same way that ANSI does nationally.

Representing ANSI in ISO, Committee Z-39 is in a good position to have U.S. information-handling standards considered for adoption by the international group. CLR staff members participate in several standards working groups, nationally and internationally.

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules

The Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR), published in 1967, is a basic tool of catalogers as well as an important force for standardization. It has added immensely to the accessibility of the information in library collections in the English-speaking world and elsewhere. This year CLR made a grant to the American Library Association (ALA) in behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of AACR: representatives of ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the (British) Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress. In the seven years that have passed since AACR's publication, certain developments have mandated revision if the Code is to assist libraries attempting to respond to changes in the modern world. Among these developments are the urgent need for reconciliation of differences in the North American and British editions, the number of international standards recently developed, and the cataloging problems presented by relatively new kinds of materials now entering the collections, e.g., audiovisual materials. It is anticipated that the work required for the revision will take two years, with publication to follow shortly thereafter.

Ohio College Library Center

The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), which became an operating system for Ohio libraries in the early '70s, today serves over 500 libraries in 35 states. A Council grant to OCLC in May (the

fourth since 1970) will assist it in the design and development of acquisitions and authority file subsystems and in contracting for the use of Battelle Memorial Institute's successful free text search system, called BASIS.

With the acquisitions subsystem, member libraries will be able to search on-line to determine whether wanted items are already on hand or on order. The subsystem will then, if appropriate, automatically prepare order forms, process invoices, issue claims for orders not received, and account for funds. It will also provide fiscal and statistical reports for management.

It is expected that the authority file subsystem will, when developed, record the authoritative form of names together with cross-references to other versions. The names in the authority file will be linked to the bibliographic records in which those names appear. Also scheduled are studies of the utility of authority files in on-line systems from various points of view and of the relative costs of various approaches to their design.

If Battelle's BASIS system can be integrated into the OCLC system, it will permit free text searching on words in bibliographic records in varying combinations of search terms. With its addition to the existing OCLC capabilities, OCLC will be able to offer its member libraries a more than ample combination of search methods.

Western Interstate Bibliographic Network

The Council has made a grant to the Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education (WICHE) for the design and development of a 17-state (plus British Columbia) Western Interstate Bibliographic Network.

The CLR funds will enable a small staff to work full time for a year on the overall design of a system which is intended to be compatible with other developing systems as well as with the evolving national system. During the course of the grant, the WICHE staff group will develop the specifications for the management, membership, legal and financial structure of the network; develop the specifications for the technical, telecommunication, and data-base structure of the network, including determination of detailed operating costs; communicate information about the services, products, costs of the proposed network to potential members and procure letters of intent to participate in it; and prepare requirements and cost estimates for the activities described above.

The Council believes it is important at this stage of the evolution of a network system that a variety of networks should be developed, separate but compatible.

Southeastern Library Network

Another regional network is the Southeastern Library Network (SOLINET), now in its second year. It has to its credit \$280,000 in first year membership fees, a \$600,000 grant from the Mellon Foundation, a cooperative agreement with the well-established and viable Southern Regional Education Board for certain aspects of administration, and a \$10,000 CLR grant toward a training program for librarians participating in the network. SOLINET member libraries are now receiving services from OCLC. However, with proper management and careful planning, SOLINET has the potential to become a significant regional node in the national bibliographic network of the future.

Stanford University -- BALLOTS

A new Council grant to Stanford University is enabling BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-Sharing System) to undertake required development tasks toward completion of a reliable, flexible, and comprehensive on-line network to support and improve services in the Stanford University libraries and, by extension, in other California libraries. The WICHE Western Bibliographic Network discussed above is also considering the possibility of tying in with BALLOTS as it moves ahead with its plans.

Under terms of the new thirty-month grant, BALLOTS staff will alter the software and file structure to support the complete MARC character set, broaden the tape communication system, and expand the comprehensive on-line technical processing services in the Stanford libraries, using the university's central computer -- an IBM 360/67. At the heart of the system is a 400,000 record file which is accessible through a powerful set of indexes. Currently these indexes provide access to a file of Library of Congress MARC data, a file of individual items being acquired and cataloged by Stanford, an on-line catalog of all the items cataloged through the BALLOTS system, and an on-line catalog of the entire undergraduate library holdings.

For the acquisitions department, BALLOTS currently supports the ordering, claiming, cancelling, receiving, and in-process control of monograph materials arriving on regular or standing orders; the receiving and in-process control of materials received on approval or blanket order plans, by exchange, or as gifts; and the ordering, claiming, and cancelling of serials.

For the catalog department, the system is supporting the in-process control, cataloging, and records maintenance of all materials cataloged in the Roman alphabet or normally transliterated.

University of Chicago

A new Council grant this year to the University of Chicago is for the purpose of enabling the University's comprehensive library data management system to achieve full operational status in 1976 and to be available for sharing with other libraries. When completed, the Chicago system is expected to perform a full range of administrative and reader services via the library's Varian minicomputer, which will have direct access to the single integrated data file stored in the University's central computer -- an IBM 370/168.

The CLR grant to the University will be spread out over a 17-month period, during which time it is expected that the system will be fully incorporated into the library structure and budget. Until such incorporation occurs, other systems and efforts must be maintained in the library and the costs of dual systems and staffing must be borne.

Bibliographic records in the Chicago system are to be fully compatible with Library of Congress MARC records and hence adaptable for use in other systems, including those supported by CLR. It is hoped that the Chicago system will prove transferable for use by other large libraries or by groups of libraries connected to a central facility via remote terminals.

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CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active during 1974-75 in this area follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control, \$22,000 (February 10, 1975).

American Library Association, \$111,431 (March 12, 1975), on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for Revision of Anglo-American Cataloging Rules.

Boston Theological Institute, \$1,000 (March 17, 1975), to assist with an effort to encourage publishers to imprint the International Standard Serial Number on the cover of serials in religion and theology.

Conversion of Serials Project (CONSER), \$250,000 (November 2, 1974, April 27, 1975).

Library of Congress, \$106,132 (November 2, 1974), for the expansion of the bibliographic services now provided to the nation's libraries through automated means by LC.

Library of Congress, \$118,600 (June 24, 1975), with an NEH matching grant of \$118,600, toward creation of a national serials data base in the humanities in machine-readable form.

Ohio College Library Center, \$124,250 (May 13, 1975), for further development of the OCLC system.

Stanford University, \$348,800 (March 12, 1975), further support for BALLOTS.

University of Chicago, \$350,000 (February 5, 1975), for final development and testing of the Library Data Management System.

Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education, \$79,325 (June 17, 1975), first steps in the development of the Western Interstate Bibliographic Network.

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE July 1, 1974

American Library Association, \$10,500 (December 6, 1962), for the publication of a compilation of federal and state legislation and for biennial supplements. Receipts from sales have been used for a third and fourth edition and supplements, and will support future similar publications.

Southeastern Library Network, \$10,000 (May 21, 1974), for partial support of program to train librarians to participate in SOLINET system.

University of North Carolina, \$14,000 (November 21, 1973), \$14,000 (June 10, 1975), toward continued underwriting of the expenses of ANSI Committee Z-39.

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

Bucknell University, \$28,000 (May 9, 1973), to permit an experiment in which students will use already available terminals to search the entire data base of the library on-line. Work has been completed and a report received.

Joint CLR-NSF Conference on National Bibliographic Control, \$4,275 (February 11, 1974).

National Bibliographic Data Base, \$200,000 authorized (November 10, 1973), \$60,000 appropriated, for programs leading to the development of a national bibliographic data base. Unspent funds have been more specifically allocated.

National Book Committee, Inc., \$5,000 (May 8, 1973), to support a one-day conference on aggregate impact of present public policies on libraries and the free flow of books and periodicals. Financial and substantive reports have been received.

Ohio College Library Center, \$194,000 (December 5, 1972), for further development of OCLC's computerized regional system.

Southwestern Library Association, \$50,000 (January 4, 1973), further development of six-state cooperative program.

Stanford University, \$325,000 (June 23, 1972), with an NEH matching grant of \$325,000 for work on BALLOTS.

University of Chicago, \$400,000 (June 8, 1970), with an NEH matching grant of \$400,000, for its data management system.

MANAGEMENT

Almost without exception the programs discussed in this annual report were developed and funded because they met the requirements of two standards the Council has followed in determining its direction and in selecting projects for support: Does the work show promise of providing a solution to a significant library problem? Will it enable libraries to use their funds economically and efficiently and thus serve scholars and other users more effectively? This latter point becomes increasingly important in the present economic situation, when inflation and rising personnel costs each year take a larger bite out of the library's budget. Several university librarians have reported that in the last few years they have had to reduce their expenditures for books and periodicals by about 30 percent. Others are in the same plight. If this situation is not reversed, irretrievable damage will be done to the collections and consequently to scholarship and the advancement of knowledge.

It is true that the activities described in the previous section have a strong relationship to the effective use of funds. However, the other responsibilities facing the directors of large academic and research libraries on a day-to-day basis require a different kind of approach, a broad program that attempts to assist them in dealing with the management problems that arise in library after library.

As early as 1968 the Council embarked on discussions centering on how best to help academic libraries redirect their

management procedures into proven efficient methods. Because the techniques of good administration developed for business and government cannot be applied unaltered to a service-oriented institution like the library, during the early stages of the overall program the Council worked with topflight management specialists to help them gain an understanding of the nature of libraries and their needs.

Recognizing that the success of the program depended on having at least the acquiescence of the universities of which academic libraries are a part, the Council from the beginning involved top academic administrators intimately in the planning process. The first significant grant was to the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) for a preliminary study by Booz, Allen & Hamilton of management practices in large university libraries. An advisory committee of university librarians and presidents worked with the study team every step of the way in what proved to be a remarkably effective partnership, and the resultant report provided a useful foundation for further efforts to improve management practices.

The study also led to the establishment within ARL of the very effective Office of University Library Management Studies, now in its fifth year and supported chiefly by Council funds. The office director (a librarian) received his on-the-job management training as a full-time member of the Booz, Allen team that carried out the next phase of the overall program: the CLR-funded study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries.

Office of University Library Management Studies

Scheduled to complete its fifth year in the fall, ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS) has been of assistance to virtually all of its constituency (and to nonmembers of ARL as well) with its practical research and development, organizational training programs, and information exchange via the Systems Procedure Exchange Center's kits and flyers. These activities are being continued under terms of a new three-year CLR grant.

One of the Office's most significant contributions has been the Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP), a carefully structured design for library management self-studies. Library personnel conducting the MRAP studies are aided by members of the OMS staff. The reviews have had an important impact well beyond the libraries themselves. In attempting to respond to some of the questions raised in the study process, the parent institutions have frequently found it necessary to review their own goals, plans, patterns, and procedures and to take another -- generally more realistic -- look at the library as a component of the total academic community. In view of the stepchild role so often assigned to the library, a top-level administrative assessment of its place and purpose cannot fail to be helpful. Twenty-one research libraries have participated in MRAP to date, and this intensive evaluation of management practices will be undertaken by other libraries in the years ahead.

New programs under consideration by OMS and its advisory group, the ARL Management Commission, are: (1) study of the public services function in research libraries, (2) design of a performance audit technique, and (3) development of specialized training packages

for application in research libraries. Members of the ARL Management Commission are the library directors of Columbia University, the universities of Chicago and California (at Berkeley), and the Smithsonian Institution. Dr. Herman Fussler, who serves the Council as consultant, will work with the Office during the period of this new grant to sharpen its direction and goals.

From the time the first CLR grant for the Office was made, ARL itself has always made some contribution to its expenses. This has gradually been increased with each succeeding year, and during the last year of the new grant, well over half of the cost of operating the Office will be met by the ARL contribution and by receipts from the sale of OMS publications and services.

As one library director has said, "The influence of the Council's initiatives in the field of management through the ARL has extended far beyond those university libraries which have participated directly in one of the specific programs of the Office of Management Studies. As a result of these timely activities a healthy interest in the management of complex institutions has spread through the university library community at just the time when economic pressures are demanding increased skill in order to maintain the support of teaching and research."

In the area of management, as with national library service and automation, the Council does not believe that there is only one way to approach a goal. Thus, in addition to the support given to early management studies of university libraries and to the creation of the ARL Office of University Library Management Studies, the

Council has provided funds for projects that attempt to solve the problems through other means. Two such approaches are described below, one of a research and development unit within a library, the other a library planning office. Their example should be of service to other institutions seeking ways to help the library make an effective contribution to the learning process.

Joint University Libraries

The CLR-sponsored research and development unit of the Joint University Libraries (JUL) of Nashville, Tennessee, now in its sixth year, continues to be helpful to JUL and its constituent libraries (Vanderbilt University, Peabody and Scarritt colleges). In-house activities this year have ranged from professional evaluation and affirmative action to statistical studies of library users from institutions other than JUL members.

Columbia University

Columbia University's Library Planning Office, now at the end of its third and last year of CLR support, is working closely with the various divisions of the library in order to extend library and information service planning capabilities at the University. In the course of this year much important work has been undertaken, including analysis of the Rare Book and Manuscript Library, the East Asian Library, and the Law Library. A financial analysis task force has been created to identify major functional applications of funds within the libraries, recommend areas of potential cost reduction, identify constraints in effecting change and recommend means to overcome them, and identify opportunities for funding to

aid in the process of change. The task force will disseminate its findings to the staff as a means of stimulating staff contributions to improved cost effectiveness. The University is committed to continued support of the Planning Office as a permanent unit of the library structure.

Moderate-sized Academic Libraries

In keeping with its charter, the Council's major concern continues to be the large academic/research library. But, with inflation of both dollars and documents creating management problems in the libraries of hundreds of smaller institutions of higher learning as well, a new project has been added -- this one aimed at the broad development of the mid-sized academic library. As a first step, the Council has made a grant to the University of North Carolina at Charlotte for a project to design and test an academic library development program. A major product is expected to be a library self-study manual for possible use by the nation's small- to moderate-sized academic libraries. A self-study of this sort should be helpful to those libraries as they review their goals, their functions, and practices with the purpose of increasing library effectiveness and improving the allocation and use of available resources. Drawing on the MRAP experience and with the OMS director available as a consultant, principles of sound practice, tailored to meet the specific needs of this group of institutions, will be developed to aid in assessing the budget processes and financial support provided the library, internal library planning and control routine, and the organizational, supervisory, personnel, and service practices of the library.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "Management" follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

Academic Library Development Program (Council administered), \$100,000 (Nov. 2, 1974) for projects that will assist in the development and management of small- to medium-sized academic libraries.

- a. University of North Carolina at Charlotte, \$47,046 of the above grant was allocated (May 27, 1975) for the design and testing of an academic library development program.

Association of Research Libraries (ARL), \$210,000 (April 30, 1975), for continuation of the Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS) for three years, beginning October 1, 1975.

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY 1, 1974

Association of Research Libraries (ARL), \$210,505 (November 21, 1972), toward support of ARL Office of University Library Management Studies for three years.

Columbia University, \$126,308 (April 14, 1972), for the Columbia University Library Planning Office.

Vanderbilt University, in behalf of the Joint University Libraries (JUL), \$171,107 (December 2, 1969) and \$89,474 (November 30, 1971), to establish and operate a model research and development unit.

LIBRARIES AND THEIR USERS

Libraries exist to serve people. Computers, management techniques, and the like are only the mechanisms that make it possible for libraries to help users meet their educational, cultural, professional, or personal requirements for information and knowledge. In recognition of this, since its inception in 1956 the Council has expended approximately 20 percent of its available program funds on projects that respond to the fact that each type of library and each library in a type has a special clientele whose requirements must be identified and met. Substantial sums have been invested in projects dealing with such diverse subjects as nontraditional education and the creation of union lists and other library tools.

College Library Program

A most significant program in this area of Council activity is the College Library Program, since 1969 supported jointly with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) by a \$1,600,000 fund.

Under the program, grants are made to undergraduate institutions that submit acceptable plans-- developed cooperatively by the college administration, faculty, and library staff-- intended to enhance the library's role in the education of students in the broad area of the humanities. Each institution must commit itself over the period of the five-year grant to match the CLR-NEH contribution.

Six such grants in 1974-75 brought to twenty-three the number of colleges participating in the program. Four of the original

recipients are nearing completion of their five-year programs, and the Council and NEH are presently studying the impact of the individual projects in broadening the library's role on campus. Also nearing completion is a similar program at Wabash College, which does not accept federal funds and therefore receives support from the Council alone.

The 1974-75 recipients and their five-year plans are:

Clark College of Atlanta, Georgia, intends to make it possible for librarians to share their expertise via team teaching. The teams are composed of instructors in its freshman studies program and graduate library assistants from neighboring Atlanta University's School of Library Science. It is anticipated that expanded usage of the library by the students will also add to their reading skills.

Kearney State College of Nebraska is also aiming its program at freshmen. Through the five-year project the college hopes to provide approximately 1,200 freshman English students each year with the experience of learning the organized general search process necessary for all levels of research. Another important goal is to develop ways in which this search process can be incorporated into the departmental curriculum.

Mills College of California has developed a program to focus attention on and encourage the use of humanities materials in the library, including those in the rare books and manuscripts collection. A project librarian has been added to the library staff, who serves as curator of the rare books collection. She has developed bibliographic courses, field trips, and special events intended to help the collection become a basic element in the college's instructional program.

Pacific University of Oregon will build on its library's experience with a tutoring program for disadvantaged students in carrying out a project for all students entitled "Maximum Instructional Effectiveness through Maximum Usage of Library Materials." An English department faculty member, reporting directly to the librarian, works with an instructional aide in diagnosing learning problems among students, matching some of the students with "peer tutors." The faculty member also attempts to acquaint the students with librarians in order to dispel any reluctance they may have to ask for assistance in the library.

University of Kentucky is providing liaison between the library and the General Studies Division of the university under a new library services coordinator. The coordinator teaches certain segments of courses where library experience is needed and is also

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available for instructing and advising individual students about term papers and research projects.

University of Utah is enlarging its staff to include an orientation coordinator to direct a program with these major goals: (1) creation of a librarian-faculty-student effort to define library-teaching priorities; (2) locating and assisting students lacking library skills; (3) development of flexible programs of library instruction for use in classroom, workshop, tutorial, or self-instruction situations; and (4) program evaluation.

Eastern Michigan's LOEX

Directly related to the CLR-NEH College Library Program is Eastern Michigan University's Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange (LOEX), a clearinghouse for information and materials relating to academic library orientation instruction at almost 200 institutions. Begun in May 1972 as a result of Eastern Michigan's Library Outreach Orientation Program (a recipient of a CLR-NEH College Library Program grant), LOEX is broadening its services under the half-time direction of a member of the university's Center of Educational Resources faculty. Basic LOEX objectives are: (1) to facilitate communication among academic libraries with orientation and instruction programs, (2) to assist libraries in developing such programs, and (3) to aid librarians on an informal basis in their research endeavors and in furthering their education in orientation activities. The university is hopeful that Project LOEX will prove largely self-supporting by the end of the CLR grant and is in any event committed to carrying on the work as a continuing part of its service program.

Book and Periodical Selection

Careful book and periodical selection is vital if academic libraries are to contribute all they are capable of to the educational

process. In the early 1960's, the Council supported an Association of College and Research Libraries project intended to assist librarians in this important task. The project resulted in the establishment of Choice magazine, a standard selection tool today in most college and university libraries as well as in numerous public and special libraries. Published monthly, Choice is now in its twelfth year. It has been self-supporting since 1969.

In 1974-75, Choice decided to add to its services to libraries a department concerned with the evaluation of recently issued periodicals, and sought the cooperation of Evan Ira Farber, Earlham College librarian and author of Classified List of Periodicals for the College Library (5th edition published in 1972). The Council has made a small three-year grant to Earlham College toward the expense to the library of Mr. Farber's Choice column, entitled "Periodicals for College Libraries."

Core Collection Project

At the close of the fiscal year, publication of the American Library Association's (ALA) edition of Books for College Libraries was imminent. With the help of CLR, the first edition had been published in 1967. The new edition - a computerized list of the 40,000 or so essential titles for a college library - will serve libraries as a basis for qualitative analysis as well as a guide to selecting publications for their collections. The Council has been active in the planning, in monitoring the work itself, and in underwriting the overall project.

Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries

While the Council's financial investment in the public library sector over the years has not been large, in terms of impact the projects supported have been significant. A small grant to the Public Library Association of ALA is enabling that organization to prepare a "Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries." Approximately 21 articles, aimed at such specific publics as children, youth, women, students, businessmen, blacks, Spanish-speaking, etc., will be written by prominent individuals. Each article will be followed by a response from an equally prominent librarian. Goal of the project is formulation of a "statement to direct widespread attention to the American public library as an active community agent capable of meeting the real needs of real people today and in the future."

Community Information Role of Public Library

New York City's well-publicized program to link the Brooklyn Public Library's 55 branches to a computerized data bank, thus enabling them to provide available information about public services and programs on a personalized basis, unfortunately never got off the ground. The Council commitment has been withdrawn because of inaction and political uncertainty. However, the publicity surrounding the CLR commitment when made three years ago may have been helpful to other city libraries which sought and received federal funds for similar projects.

Los Angeles Public Library Study

"A Community Responsive Branch Program: A Study of Community Attitudes for the Los Angeles Library System" is the title of a report

growing out of a project that was cooperatively supported by CLR and the Educational Facilities Laboratories. With its content provided by an architect, a social psychologist, and opinion researchers, the report makes many novel recommendations of the factors that should be considered when planning new branch libraries in a large urban system.

Library Independent Study Program

Now in its third year, the College Entrance Examination Board's (CEEB) Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects is continuing its focus on public libraries already offering independent study opportunities to their constituencies. Eleven libraries have participated in the program: Atlanta, Cleveland, Denver, Enoch Pratt (Baltimore), Miami-Dade, Portland (Maine), Salt Lake City, St. Louis, Tulsa City-County, Worcester, and the Free Public Library of Woodbridge (New Jersey). During this third year of the project, a Learners' Advisory Service has been introduced at nine libraries, and data collection and evaluative questions have been set up as well. Assessment of user and services data from four of these - Atlanta, Tulsa, Portland (Maine), and Salt Lake City - shows that independent study projects have been successful both in establishing that there is a need for such services and in attracting and assisting adults with learning projects. As the nine libraries continue to expand their services, modifications are being made in order to define more explicitly an "adult learner" and describe individual learning projects; to obtain more information on staff costs in terms of time spent in preparation, interviews with learners, gathering materials, and making inquiries or referrals; and to determine the effectiveness of nationally prepared versus locally

created advertising. The Office is funded by CLR, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and U. S. Office of Education, as well as by the CEEB itself.

Support of Indexes

From time to time, the Council assists in the preparation of a specialized index or guide for librarians and their constituents. In 1974-75, such assistance took the form of nominal aid to Professor Donald M. Jacobs for expenses in preparing photo-ready manuscript of his index to black newspapers published before the Civil War, and a more sizable grant to the American Society for Information Science (ASIS) toward preparation of a 25-year cumulative index of the Journal of the American Society for Information Science (JASIS), to be available in both book and machine-readable form.

The JASIS index will approximate a "core collection" of information science periodical literature. It is expected that the project will develop generally accepted indexing terminology and standards which will prove valuable to the profession as a whole. As a condition of the CLR grant, ASIS has agreed that the JASIS cumulative index in book and computer tape form will be made available at a moderate price, commensurate with a reasonable recovery of costs and overhead, and that a percentage of any profits from sales will be earmarked for future updates.

Users in Government

The University of the State of New York's Council-supported study of information needs of state government is nearing completion and is engendering considerable interest among state librarians, researchers,

and budget analysts. According to the university's June report, 60 persons attending a May 2 workshop were so enthusiastic about the findings that they have volunteered to form a working committee to foster greater visibility of agency information resources and improved interlibrary loan procedures between agency libraries and the New York State Library. The report concludes: "The survey of state agency information resources has been completed and is being edited.... Sufficient interest has been generated in this survey that we expect to publish it, using other funds, in the form of a directory of existing resources."

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "Libraries and Their Users" follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

American Library Association (ALA), \$8,372 (July 1, 1974), toward preparation and publication of a consumers' handbook for public libraries.

American Society for Information Science (ASIS), \$19,910 (May 13, 1975), toward a 25-year cumulative index to the Journal of The American Society for Information Science (JASIS).

Earlham College, \$7,500 (February 21, 1975), for three-year nonpersonnel expense assistance in preparing a regular Choice magazine column on periodical selection.

Eastern Michigan University, \$42,771 (November 2, 1974), to support expansion of its Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange (LOEX) over the next three years.

Donald M. Jacobs, \$500 (December 23, 1974), for expenses in preparing photo-ready manuscript of his index to black newspapers published before the Civil War.

National Endowment for the Humanities, \$100,000 (May 22, 1975), with an NEH matching grant of \$100,000, for further funding of the joint CLR-NEH College Library Program.

Projects funded under the CLR-National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) College Library Program (in each case, the total grant is matched by the institution):

Clark College, \$50,000 - \$25,000 each from CLR and NEH
(May 9, 1975).

Kearney State College, \$46,000 - \$23,000 each from CLR and NEH
(May 9, 1975).

Mills College, \$48,608 - \$24,304 each from CLR and NEH
(September 12, 1974).

Pacific University, \$50,000 - \$25,000 each from CLR and NEH
(May 9, 1975).

University of Kentucky, \$50,000 - \$25,000 each from CLR and NEH
(September 13, 1974).

University of Utah, \$51,000 - \$25,500 each from CLR and NEH
(May 9, 1975).

ON-GOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY 1, 1974

American Association for State and Local History, \$10,000
(January 25, 1972), for the preparation of a book on the collection, care, and use of photographs.

American Association for State and Local History, \$34,604 (April 17, 1970), for the preparation of a manual on the care of manuscript collections.

American Association of Law Libraries, \$20,000 (November 8, 1968), to conduct an annual statistical survey of law library resources in the United States and Canada.

Etta Armtzen, \$8,000 (January 26, 1971), for a revision of the original 1959 edition of Mary W. Chamberlin's Guide to Art Reference Books.

College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB), \$150,000 (January 4, 1973), in support of its newly established Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects.

Patricia K. Grimsted, \$12,739 (June 15, 1971), Council's portion of a joint NEH-CLR grant of \$25,478 toward the preparation of a projected directory entitled "Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids." Awaiting publication.

Michigan State University, \$1,602 (August 10, 1971), for publication of a directory of university extension library services at member institutions of the National University Extension Association and the

National Association of State Universities and Land-Grant Colleges.
Awaiting publication of second edition.

New York State Information Services, \$25,000 (May 29, 1974), toward a study of state government information needs.

Projects funded under the CLR-NEH College Library Program (in each case the Council's grant was matched by NEH and by the institution):

Brown University, \$50,000 (March 23, 1970).

Davidson College, \$25,000 (October 17, 1972).

Dillard University, \$25,000 (March 23, 1970).

Eastern Michigan University, \$25,000 (August 28, 1970).

Hampden-Sydney College, \$25,000 (October 17, 1972).

Hampshire College, \$25,000 (August 26, 1970).

Howard University, \$50,000 (September 22, 1971).

Jackson State University, \$25,000 (March 23, 1970).

Jamestown College, \$25,000 (April 13, 1973).

Manhattanville College, \$25,000 (December 3, 1973).

Miles College, \$25,000 (June 20, 1973).

North Carolina Central University, \$25,000 (March 15, 1972).

Occidental College, \$25,000 (December 10, 1973).

Swarthmore College, \$20,000 (September 8, 1971).

University of Colorado, \$37,875 (April 13, 1973).

University of Richmond, \$25,000 (June 20, 1973).

Washington and Lee University, \$25,000 (March 16, 1971).

Wabash College, \$50,000 (May 1, 1970), matched by the college, to increase effectiveness of the college library by changing its concept from that of a store of information to that of workshop of the liberal arts.

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, Inc., \$300,000 (April 27, 1972), toward the creation of citizen's

information centers in Brooklyn's 55 branch libraries. Terminated by CLR Board action.

American Library Association (ALA), \$290,502 (June 30, 1969), \$21,100 supplementary grant (August 10, 1972), for development from machine-readable records of a 40,000-title book catalog as a core collection for college libraries.

Los Angeles Public Library, \$32,000 (March 5, 1973), toward study of community attitudes about the library system and community needs, entitled "The Community Responsive Branch Program."

PRESERVATION

Preservation of library materials has always been a problem for libraries, but for tomorrow's custodians of books and periodicals the problem will be even greater, as more and more materials are added to the collections. It has been demonstrated that the paper in many of the newer books and periodicals is much more prone to deterioration than is that in other publications hundreds of years old. Council-supported research some years ago determined that acidity in paper was the primary factor in its deterioration; as papermaking technology had evolved over the centuries, the resultant product had become increasingly acid and had otherwise been progressively weakened by the chemistry and mechanics of the processes involved. In the continuing struggle against deterioration of library materials, the Council has provided support for the William J. Barrow Research Laboratory in Richmond, Va., the Preservation Research and Testing Office of the Library of Congress, and the New England Document Conservation Office. A new grant this year to the Barrow Laboratory has enabled it to continue its research activities. The Library of Congress Office and the New England Document Conservation Center are now self-supporting, with funds received from their parent organization and/or sale of services.

Barrow Laboratory

Major products of the Council's long-term support of the Barrow Laboratory have been specifications for permanent and durable paper and the Barrow one- and two-bath processes for deacidifying paper. In the last few years the Laboratory has, among other things, revised its

specifications for permanent and durable paper, evaluated the lasting qualities of the new papers which appear to be dominating the market, and investigated the effect of temperature and humidity on the useful life of paper. But the most concentrated effort has been in the development of a morpholine vapor deacidification process for books in bulk, now in the last phases of testing. In order to insure that libraries will benefit from this new development at minimum expense, the Council has arranged patenting and licensing through the nonprofit Research Corporation. CLR's royalties from this agreement, if any, would be applied to further preservation research.

Over the years the cost of operating the Barrow Laboratory has risen significantly, with annual inflationary increases of 10 percent or more predicted. The size of these figures relative to the Council's budget has caused CLR staff to investigate the possibility of obtaining supplementary funding from other grant-making organizations, particularly the National Endowment for the Humanities. At report time, NEH has informed the Council of its possible interest in providing \$100,000 to match a similar amount from CLR.

Library of Congress Preservation Office

During this year the Library of Congress informed the Council that CLR support was no longer required for the LC Preservation Research Office. The Office was activated in 1971, with the help of a \$94,500 Council grant for the purchase of equipment. In the years since, the Office has performed important services to libraries and others in addition to conducting basic research. Its final report to CLR noted that the Preservation Office "is giving high priority to large scale tests of

diethylzinc vapor as a vapor phase deacidification agent for books." Also noted was a wide range of activities engaged in by the Office -- from evaluation of the life of Xerox paper to identification of indelible ink for stamping books.

New England Document Conservation Center

The New England Document Conservation Center's final report on its two-year grant from the Council indicates that self-supporting status was reached in one and a half years of operation. Estimated income for 1974-1975 from non-CLR sources is \$236,750 -- up from \$77,148 during the first year. In addition to its restoration activities for libraries, archives, and related governmental agencies in the six-state region, the Center has become a clearinghouse for conservation information and the source to which many librarians and others turn for assistance, guidance, and instruction in the care of their materials. The Center has in a short time achieved considerable recognition, and it is the hope of the Council that the success of this model will encourage other regional groupings of libraries to undertake similar programs.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "Preservation" follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., \$240,000 (Aug. 10, 1974), toward continued operation of the Laboratory for the period July 1, 1974 - June 30, 1976.

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY, 1974

Paul Banks, \$988 (March 20, 1974), to assist in writing a manual on library conservation. Awaiting publication.

Anthony Cains, \$4,350 (May 1, 1972), to complete a workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts based on the practices of the Restoration Department of the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, Italy. Awaiting publication.

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., \$113,633 (with contingency of \$37,000) (August 1, 1973), for research on the causes of and cures for physical deterioration of library materials.

Margaret Hey, \$10,500 (December 23, 1971), to investigate book and archival paper restoration techniques along scientific lines already under way in the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome, Italy.

Library of Congress, \$95,000 (December 4, 1969), for assistance in equipping a preservation research office in the Library.

New England Interstate Library Compact, \$70,300 (December 1, 1972), to assist that six-state consortium to establish the New England Document Conservation Center.

MICROFORMS

Not all deteriorating books and journals can benefit from deacidification. Many are already in such weakened condition that their physical preservation is not feasible. For these the most effective approach is preservation of the information they contain, and micro-filming is the most efficient way of accomplishing that end. Its costs are much less than those of conventional reprinting or of any other practical method of restoring the original publications or recording their contents.

Microfilm offers other important benefits to libraries. It provides a means of greatly reducing the storage requirements for bulky and voluminous materials such as newspapers; it also affords a relatively inexpensive means of reproducing and disseminating materials for which the demand is small or unpredictable.

In the most recently published Academic Library Statistics (1973-74) of the Association of Research Libraries, it is noted that the median collection of total microform units held by its 82 university library members jumped from 290,944 to 733,755 in the six-year period between 1967-68 and 1973-74. A decade ago -- 1963-64 -- the microform unit collections were not even referred to in the annual statistical reports. As for microfilming for preservation, the Library of Congress annual report of 1973 notes that at LC "more than 5.7 million pages [were] prepared for microfilming during the year. This is more than a 400 percent increase over 1968 figures."

CLR has from its inception been active in supporting, coordinating, and encouraging the utilization of microfilm and other micrographic techniques. In its early years a good deal of emphasis was placed on hardware development. More recently, the Council's focus has shifted to library applications of micrographics and other activities that provide librarians and their suppliers with practical information about microfilms and their effective use in the library. Two significant CLR-supported projects of this nature are nearing completion: the formulation of a national standard for the advertising of micropublications and the preparation of a manual that will allow persons without technical knowledge to evaluate microfiche reading machines for library usage. The manual, now being printed, will be distributed without cost to libraries and similar institutions.

The Council has for a number of years had on its staff a micrographics specialist who acts as a consultant to libraries and library organizations and also serves as a link between them and commercial interests. He is a member of the board of Directors of the National Microfilm Association and a consultant to the Micropublishing Project Committee of the American Library Association. Also, as chairman of the American National Standard Institute's subcommittee on advertising of micropublications standards, he has submitted to and had approved by the Institute's Board of Standards Review a new standard written by his subcommittee comprised of librarians and representatives of micropublishing firms. The standard provides guidance to micropublishers concerning the bibliographic and technical information needed by their customers (primarily research-oriented libraries and related institutions) in making purchasing decisions. The standard also

provides the acquisitions librarian with a checklist by which the micrographic and bibliographic suitability of any micropublication can be determined.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "Microforms" follows:

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY 1, 1974

Governors State University, \$5,138 (January 30, 1973), to assist its Learning Resources Center in a pilot project to develop, test, and evaluate an economical system for using selectively disseminated microfiche from the National Technical Information Service.

Microfiche Reader Testing Design Project (Council administered), \$10,650 (May 26, 1973), \$4,000 (April 4, 1975), for the development of a microfiche (or small set of microfiche) and an accompanying manual which will help librarians to determine inexpensively and reliably the suitability of any microfiche reader for their purposes.

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

Mega Systems Design, Ltd., \$23,400 (December 17, 1971), for development of an automatic library card camera. Prototype camera is in use, and production model is being marketed.

INTERNATIONAL

The Council's long commitment to international librarianship and archival activity continues to provide an essential element in increasing the exchange of information among the world's nations and cultures. More and more nations are able to gain access to each other's publications as bibliographic tools and techniques are standardized and accepted on a multinational basis. International cooperation abounds, as the world's foremost librarians, archivists, and information scientists meet as necessary to discuss the "next step" toward improved accessibility to all of the world's library and archival collections.

As noted in earlier reports, the Council's first grant following its formation in 1956 was to the American Library Association. The grant enabled an ALA representative to attend a meeting in Germany on the subject of international standardization of cataloging. His report of the June 1957 meeting leads off: "It is abundantly clear from talks with leading European librarians that the present is a highly favorable time to attempt international standardization of cataloging rules. There is a readiness to accept as a starting point the 1955 findings of the IFLA subcommittee on standardization of cataloging rules which was headed by Frank Francis of the British Museum."

International Federation of Library Associations

Throughout most of its existence the Council has worked within the framework of the International Federation of Library Associations

(IFLA) in pursuit of international library cooperation. CLR staff and board members, in their private capacity, have participated in its decision making as officers and consultants. CLR grants, including two new ones in 1974-75, have played a vital role in the organization's growth and viability in the 1970s. The participation of volunteers is essential to any association's success, but equally important is executive staffing to coordinate the volunteers and to carry out the decisions made by elected officers. The IFLA Secretariat, established with CLR assistance in 1971 and partially supported by it since, is approaching the self-sustaining stage, and has fully justified the Council's investment of funds and the investment of their invaluable time and energy by librarians from many countries.

At IFLA's 40th General Council Meeting, held in Washington, D.C., in November 1974 and supported in part with a CLR grant, "National and International Library Planning" was the theme. Professor Robert Vosper of the University of California at Los Angeles -- an IFLA vice president, conference chairman, and a CLR board member -- noted in an introductory working document for the meeting: "It is clear that successful national library planning requires first of all the international linkage that a mutually agreed upon and usable universal bibliographic record can provide. This is the theme of this 1974 conference, and that interactive theme of national and international planning is made clear in the several formal papers on the agenda. The leadership of Unesco and the Council on Library Resources, focused through IFLA's professional competence, have moved us to this exciting point in bibliothecal history. To the Council goes particular credit for fostering the steady march toward international

standards for cataloging ever since the Paris Conference of 1961 and the prior planning for that landmark setting."

Universal Bibliographic Control

At the Washington IFLA Meeting, the new quarterly IFLA Journal was introduced, replacing the IFLA News. The lead article in this issue is "IFLA's Programme for UBC (Universal Bibliographic Control): the Background and the Basis" by Dorothy Anderson, director of the IFLA International Office of UBC. UBC's objective is a single bibliographic record -- created only once, ideally at its source -- for each item of knowledge published anywhere in the world. As director of the IFLA Cataloguing Secretariat, supported in part by the Council throughout its existence, and editor of its quarterly, International Cataloguing, Mrs. Anderson has been at the forefront of the continuing effort for UBC. She wrote: "It is apparent that this positive action of the IFLA Executive Board could not have been contemplated and certainly could not have been carried out without the prospect of financial support. This has, indeed, been forthcoming: the Council on Library Resources, Washington, D.C., has shown understanding of the problems of UBC and the proposed programme of action and has also revealed its confidence in IFLA's ability to carry out that programme by making a generous grant for the first year of operation."

The Council has extended its support of the IFLA International Office for UBC for two additional years through June 30, 1977. In its first year (July 1974-June 1975), the Office has measured up to most expectations for the period. Its wide range of activities included specialist cataloging projects; regional seminars on national bibliographies;

sponsoring, editing, and publishing cataloging manuals and recommended standards; consulting services; and publication of the quarterly International Cataloguing. The UBC office will continue to receive office space and services from the British Library, as well as grants from Unesco, several national library and bibliographic organizations, and income from sale of its publication.

It is worth noting that, in a worldwide context, the Council's work in attempting to achieve national bibliographic control becomes even more significant. For any universal system will have to rely on the completeness and accuracy of individual national units for its effectiveness.

International Council on Archives

Encouraged in some measure by the successes of IFLA, the Council has looked favorably at a request from the International Council on Archives (ICA) for support to strengthen its relatively new secretariat. A three-year grant has been made to ICA to make possible the addition to the secretariat staff of an executive assistant and a bilingual secretary. They will aid the executive director and relieve in part the volunteer archivists whose extensive contributed efforts have been largely responsible for the work of the organization since its establishment in 1950. It is expected that with a strengthened full-time staff, this world organization of the archival profession will be able to expand its programs in such areas as: (1) the development and training of archivists, (2) the microfilming and preservation of materials, and (3) the publishing of guides to the sources of history of nations. In addition to receiving dues support from the world's archives, the ICA

Secretariat is housed at no cost in the French National Archives. An expected increase in dues, anticipated royalties from its publications, and additional grants and contracts from international bodies are expected to make the ICA self-supporting at the termination of the CLR grant on June 30, 1978.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of CLR international activities projects active in 1974-75 follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

Hans-Peter Geh, \$3,500 (July 18, 1974), to enable Dr. Geh, director of Wurtembergische Landesbibliothek, Stuttgart, West Germany, to engage in a study tour of major U.S. libraries and to report his impressions to the Council. (Completed.)

Unesco, \$2,200 (September 4, 1974), to provide one fellowship for a participant from a developing country in an international summer school supported in part by Unesco's Division of Scientific and Technological Information and Documentation.

International Council on Archives, \$72,000 (May 5, 1975), for partial support of ICA Secretariat for a three-year period.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$45,000 (March 19, 1975), for continued support of the IFLA Secretariat through January 30, 1976.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$144,200 (May 5, 1975), continued support of the IFLA Office for Universal Bibliographic Control.

Travel Funds, \$3,500 (November 2, 1974), additional contribution to CLR fund which enables important foreign librarians to visit the United States when their presence is essential for the purpose of carrying out selected tasks.

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY 1, 1974

Valerie Bloomfield, \$10,000 (Council-administered) (August 14, 1973), for a study of significant private research libraries in England, particularly those in London.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$70,000 (May 13, 1974), to support the establishment of a worldwide system for the organized exchange of bibliographic information (UBC).

International Federation of Library Associations, \$45,000 (December 20, 1973), toward continued support of IFLA Secretariat.

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

International Association of Law Libraries (IALL), \$2,500 (May 17, 1974), to enable five law librarians from developing countries to attend the IALL 5th International Course in Law Librarianship in Washington, D.C., November 1974.

International Association of School Librarianship, \$1,850 (April 5, 1974), toward support of association's Singapore meeting, July 1974.

International Federation for Documentation, \$1,680 (March 28, 1974), toward support of Executive Committee meeting in Washington, D.C., November 1974.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$3,500 (November 14, 1973) in travel funds to enable participants to attend two meetings of the Committee on Cataloguing's Working Group on Content Designators held in Brussels in February and in Helsinki in May 1974.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$10,000 (June 30, 1973), for support of secretariat to plan and organize the November 1974 conference held in Washington, D.C. Additional funds were provided by other organizations.

International Federation of Library Associations, \$54,000 (June 30, 1971), to establish a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing as a center to promote and coordinate the international standardization of cataloging practices.

National Archives and Records Service, \$4,000 (February 28, 1974), partial support of the International Seminar on Public Records Management held in Washington, March 1974.

National Book Committee, Inc., \$9,000 (July 17, 1972), partial support of a conference on the role of library services and educational materials in education programs in developing countries.

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

The quality of library programs and services is in direct correlation to the quality of the librarians who administer them. It is for this reason that the Council has increasingly worked with library leaders in developing opportunities for young and mid-career librarians to improve their skills in their chosen field. The oldest CLR-supported professional development program now in existence is the Fellowship Program which began in 1968. Then, a year and a half ago, the Council announced its Academic Library Management Intern Program as well as a formal master's degree program at the Graduate Library School of the University of Chicago for individuals who have earned doctorates in other fields and are seriously interested in devoting their talents to library work. And in April of this year, the Council approved an Advanced Study Program for Librarians, designed to further the development of subject specialists for the nation's research and academic libraries.

The selection procedures and standards in all of these programs are rigorous. Applications undergo a preliminary review by distinguished librarians, with the CLR Fellowship Committee taking their recommendations into careful consideration in making the final choices. In the case of the interns and advanced study award recipients, the Selection Committee members interview the leading candidates before making their final decisions.

Advanced Study Program

The new Advanced Study Program will enable up to five qualified librarians to pursue a year of full-time graduate course work in a scholarly discipline -- one traditionally considered to be within the "liberal arts and sciences" -- at a graduate school of distinction in the chosen field of study. The program is not intended to support work in professional areas such as library science, business administration, computer science, or management, nor may the funds be used for travel or for writing a dissertation. The awards cover formal graduate study for one academic year (1976-77), with successful candidates receiving stipends of up to \$15,000 -- based on salary and normal benefits received from the home institution for a comparable period during 1975-76 -- plus graduate tuition fees for two semesters or three quarters and some assistance for necessary moving costs.

University of Chicago Library Program for Ph.D.s

This program, like the Advanced Study Program, was instituted in order to attempt to meet a need that had frequently been called to our attention by directors of large research libraries -- a need for competent and highly qualified subject specialists to work with scholars and other students in various aspects of the liberal arts. It is still too soon to measure the success of the University of Chicago program, which is aimed at assisting a limited number of Ph.D. holders in nonlibrary fields to earn an M.A. in library science. That will have to await

a report on the postgraduate employment history of the nine students -- six in 1974-75 and three in 1975-76 -- who will have been trained under the program. Any such evaluation will, of course, have to take into consideration the state of the job market for librarians during the period in question.

Academic Library Management Program

The Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program, now nearing completion of its first year, holds great promise of contributing to the development of some of the talented professionals who will manage the nation's great libraries in the future. By working closely with the director and top staff of one of the nation's leading academic libraries, each intern receives a firsthand exposure to situations that will help supply the skills and techniques required by a leadership job in an academic library.

The internship experience is well described in the final report made to the Council by Ralph M. Edwards, who was assistant director of Western Michigan University's School of Librarianship before beginning his intern year. He writes, in part: "When I arrived at the University of Michigan Library last September, my conceptions of what I would be doing and of how it would be of specific value to me were quite vague. What I felt I needed most was a chance to put theory into practice, and I imagined the internship as an opportunity to practice management with close and expert guidance. My poorly formulated expectations were a good example of how little we usually think through ahead

of time those situations that we are facing for the first time. I certainly had the background theory, understanding, and experience to realize, had I given the time and effort to thinking about it, that an internship in the traditional sense in which I was conceiving it could rarely, if ever, be a practical possibility in administration.

"An internship implied to me the practice of that which was being learned. The practice of the intern is, of course, monitored and guided by a teacher/expert because the intern is still a beginner with much to learn. It took me some time to realize and accept the fact that this traditional conception of an internship is inappropriate to management for the rather obvious reason that the practice of management requires authority, and managerial authority at the level at which I needed practice cannot be reassigned easily and for short periods of time. ... Under these circumstances it was, of course, neither feasible nor desirable to put us into positions of authority that would have permitted us really to be management interns practicing management.

"But what I did come to realize after some conceptual adjustments was that the position in which I found myself offered opportunities for types of learning activity different from what I had been expecting and that these activities were ones that I could not have experienced nearly as effectively, if at all, in any practicing management position."

For the second round of awards, more than 300 requests for 1975-76 management intern applications were received at the CLR offices, and over 50 librarians completed the application

procedure. Selected from the 12 finalists following personal interviews were:

Linda Beaupré, coordinator of public services at the undergraduate library of the University of California at Berkeley, who will intern with Richard De Gennaro of the University of Pennsylvania;

Jean W. Boyer, chief of collection development at Temple University, assigned to Page Ackerman of the University of California at Los Angeles;

George C. Grant, associate director of public services at the Southern Illinois Library, who will work with Rutherford B. Rogers of Yale University;

Robert Koester, assistant professor and head of the undergraduate reference library at the University of Tennessee, who will intern with Columbia University's Warren J. Haas; and

Lee Ann Putnam, associate librarian at Gallaudet College, assigned to Virginia P. Whitney of Rutgers University.

A June meeting at the Council's offices brought together the first group of five interns, their librarian hosts, and two of the three new hosts for 1975-76. As they discussed their experiences, the comments of librarians and interns alike seemed to justify overwhelmingly the existence of the management program. One of the host directors noted at the meeting's conclusion: "I think not only the librarians and the interns felt the program was successful - staffs have profited as well."

CLR Fellowship Program

The Council's formal support of professional development for librarians began in a modest manner in 1968 with a fellowship program for librarians. Including those librarians selected for CLR Fellowships in 1975-76, 165 awards (totalling a little more than half a million dollars) have been announced in the past seven years. Events have

served to justify many of the Council's choices; a surprisingly large number of fellows have moved on to more important library posts, the latest of these being the newly appointed university librarian at Princeton and the new director of libraries at MIT. The 26 new recipients will devote from three to nine months on self-developed study and research projects in areas ranging from computer-based reference service in academic libraries to the administration of rare book and special collections departments in large public university libraries. As in previous years, CLR Fellows will receive funds for approved travel, supplies, and services from the Council, and an appropriate leave of absence from their employers to carry out their projects.

It was hoped that the Fellowship Program would encourage institutions to develop leave of absence opportunities for librarians comparable to faculty sabbaticals. While the recipients of the CLR grants have received leaves, it is not possible at present to judge the broader impact of the program on institutional policies.

The 26 recipients of Council on Library Resources fellowships for the academic year 1975-76 and their projects are as follows:

Judith Armstrong, director of the library, Drury College (Mo.). Survey of attitudes, employment practices, and the progress of affirmative action programs for women in libraries.

Pauline Atherton, professor, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University. A survey of the real and potential impact of computer-based reference service in academic libraries.

Martha J. Bailey, physics librarian, Purdue University. A study of the position of the middle manager in the academic library organization.

Boyd M. Bolvin, associate dean of instruction, Bellevue Community College (Wash.). An examination of external degree programs in higher education in the U.S.

Keith M. Cottam, assistant director of the Undergraduate Library, University of Tennessee at Knoxville. A study of the issues involved in the utilization of specialists in large academic libraries with emphasis on technical specialists.

Doris C. Dale, associate professor, Department of Instructional Materials, Southern Illinois University at Carbondale. To gather data and information about community college libraries for a book on current trends and practices and to enrich her background for courses taught in this area.

Lynn C. Dennison, professional assistant, Association of College and Research Libraries, American Library Association, Chicago. To gather information on organizational patterns in library and media services in community and junior colleges and to evaluate these patterns in terms of their usefulness in meeting information needs of users.

Barbara L. Feret, director of the library, Culinary Institute of America, Hyde Park, New York. To survey, identify, and analyze strengths of important historically-oriented collections on gastronomy and cookery.

Thelma Freides, associate professor, School of Library Service, Atlanta University. Preparation of a bibliographic guide to the reports which officials of the federal government are required to submit to Congress.

Wolfgang M. Freitag, fine arts Librarian, Harvard College Library, Harvard University. To complete work on and prepare for publication a manuscript of about 150 printed pages for "Sources of Information in the Humanities."

Jane C. Henning, head, Howe Architecture Library, Arizona State University at Tempe. A study of libraries associated with schools of architecture in the United States.

Judith Holliday, librarian, Fine Arts Library, Cornell University. To complete a holdings list of the 19th century American architectural periodicals.

Richard G. Landon, assistant head, Thomas Fisher Rare Book Library, University of Toronto. A study of the administration of rare book and special collections departments in large public university libraries.

Alan H. MacDonald, health sciences librarian, Dalhousie University (Halifax, N.S.). To study the various organizational

models which universities have adopted to accommodate the "special" circumstances of professional school libraries.

James W. McGregor, head of the library's technical services, Northeastern Illinois University. To study staffing for serials processing in large university libraries.

Joan K. Marshall, chief of the library's Catalog Division, Brooklyn College. The construction of a thesaurus of non-sexist subject headings.

Ann F. Painter, professor, Graduate School of Library Science, Drexel University. To determine the functions of traditional library classifications in research libraries in the United States..

James F. Parks, Jr., head librarian, Millsaps College (Miss.). To carry out an internship at the Georgia Institute of Technology.

Stephen L. Peterson, librarian, Divinity School, Yale University. To do basic research for a bibliographic guide to Protestant missions.

Eugene E. Petriwsky, assistant director for technical services, University of Colorado Library. To study the effect of proposed changes in the 8th edition of the Library of Congress List of Subject Headings on medium-sized academic libraries.

Hannelore B. Rader, orientation librarian, Eastern Michigan University. To study 10 successful library instruction programs in academic libraries and summarize findings in the form of a guide.

Donald L. Roberts, audiovisual librarian, Hennepin County Library (Edina, Minn.). To examine past and present censorship of nonbook media in public libraries.

Earl R. Schwass, library director, Naval War College (Newport, R. I.). To study user education programs of senior military and graduate school libraries with particular reference to the needs of midcareer military officers.

Patricia H. Shoyinka, cataloger, Ibadan University Library, Ibadan, Nigeria. To study the use of MARC records for catalog production in selected North American libraries in order to determine basic criteria for the use of MARC records in Nigeria.

Mildred C. Tietjen, director of library services, Georgia Southwestern College. To compare and evaluate instructional programs at ALA-accredited graduate library schools.

Joyce L. White, librarian, Penniman Library of Education, University of Pennsylvania. To organize available information on church libraries in order to produce a reference tool on church libraries.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "Professional Development" follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

Academic Library Management Intern Program (Council administered), \$265,000 (Nov. 2, 1974), to continue for two more years a program to give on-the-job training each year to up to five potential directors of the nation's leading academic and research libraries.

Advanced Study Program (CLR administered), \$115,000 (May 1, 1975), to assist up to five well-qualified librarians who desire advanced formal academic training in a scholarly discipline.

CLR Fellowship Program (CLR administered), \$85,000 (Nov. 9, 1974), support for 26 CLR Fellows in 1975-76.

Travel Funds, \$5,000 (Nov. 2, 1974), additional contribution to CLR fund that enables librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to attend important overseas meetings in which they have an essential role.

ONGOING PROJECTS FUNDED BEFORE JULY 1, 1974

CLR Fellowship Program (CLR administered), \$85,000 (Nov. 10, 1973), support for 25 CLR Fellows in 1974-75.

University of Chicago Graduate Library School, \$103,000 (July 5, 1973), for a program to support present holders of the Ph.D. degree as candidates for the M.A. degree in librarianship.

GENERAL

Each year the Council makes a few grants that fail to fit any of the rather specific categories included in this report. More often than not they assist the financing of a special conference, the writing and/or editing of a book, the compilation of statistics, all in fields related to libraries. Four such grants were made in 1974-75, and a previously funded project was completed.

University of Iowa Conference

A conference on "The Publication of American Historical Manuscripts" was held in the Herbert Hoover Presidential Library of the University of Iowa, April 30 - May 1, with the assistance of the Council. It was attended by members of the National Historical Publications Commission, editors of forthcoming letterpress editions of the papers of outstanding Americans, curators of manuscript collections, and interested historians and librarians. They gathered to consider past, present, and future efforts to make the papers of notable Americans available to students and scholars. Results of the conference were considered constructive, and the Commission extended its formal thanks to CLR via a resolution adopted April 29, and signed by its chairman, James B. Rhoads, the archivist of the United States.

Library Planning and Federal Policy

Kathleen Molz, chief planning officer for library programs at the U.S. Office of Education until her resignation in 1974, sought and

received CLR support in connection with her preparation of a book tentatively titled "Federal Policy and Library Planning." It is hoped that her book will assist librarians who must deal with federal programs by increasing their awareness of the ways federal officials make decisions on planning and budgeting and on the administration of legislated programs.

Library Interiors Handbook

William S. Pierce of Pennsylvania State University was provided a small CLR grant in April to enable him to complete his already extensive travel and photography in connection with writing a book provisionally entitled "Planning the Library Interior: A Handbook." Mr. Pierce, whose responsibilities at Penn State have included library planning and furnishing, is conducting his travels during a six-month sabbatical (commencing July 1, 1975). Marcel Decker, Inc., has contracted to publish the book upon its completion on or before July 31, 1976.

Slide Libraries

Betty Jo Irvine's CLR-supported guide on slide libraries for academic institutions and museums has been published by Libraries Unlimited, Inc., of Littleton, Colorado, under the title Slide Libraries. Subject matter covered includes general background, administration and staffing, classification and cataloging, use of standard library techniques and tools, acquisition, production methods and techniques, projection systems, and miscellaneous equipment and supplies. There is also a selected bibliography of slide sources, slide libraries, and equipment manufacturers and distributors.

CLR-Supported Projects

A list of all CLR-supported projects active in 1974-75 under the heading "General" follows:

NEW GRANTS IN 1974-75

Indiana University Graduate Library School, \$972 (January 8, 1975), to conduct statistical analyses of academic libraries and their relationships to characteristics of their host institutions (1970-71 vs 1972-73), based on USOE computer tapes.

R. Kathleen Molz, \$8,000 (July 25, 1974), for assistance with a projected book on library planning and federal policy.

William S. Pierce, \$3,000 (April 1, 1975), for travel and photography expenses in connection with preparation of his book, "Planning the Library Interior."

University of Iowa, \$3,750 (December 27, 1974), partial support of conference on "The Publication of American Historical Manuscripts."

PROJECTS COMPLETED IN 1974-75

Betty Jo Irvine, \$4,389 (May 1, 1972), to prepare and edit a manual for librarians and curators giving them background information and preferred techniques in the use of slides and slide projectors.

ESTIMATED INCOME AND EXPENSE BUDGET
FISCAL YEAR 1976

INCOME

From Ford Foundation	\$1,985,000
Interest	75,000
Royalties	5,000
	<u>\$2,065,000</u>

EXPENSE

Substantive Program

Automation, Networks, Standardization, and National Library Services	\$ 800,000
Libraries and Their Users	125,000
Management	180,000
Preservation and Microforms	200,000
Professional Development	225,000
International Activities	185,000
General Program	100,000
TOTAL, Substantive Program	<u>\$1,815,000</u>

Administration

Salaries and allowances *	\$ 111,500
Benefits *	28,500
Accrued leave allowance	9,500
Rent of office space	33,000
Furniture and equipment	7,500
Insurance	2,500
Supplies	4,500
Communications	13,500
Printing and duplication	9,500
Staff travel *	6,000
Professional services	8,000
Directors' meetings	10,000
Miscellaneous	4,000
Contingency	2,000
TOTAL, Administration	<u>\$ 250,000</u>
TOTAL, Substantive and Administrative	<u>\$2,065,000</u>

*For administrative staff only

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

JULY 1, 1974 - JUNE 30, 1975

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 GEORGE A. PARSONS, Information Systems Specialist
 CARL M. SPAULDING, Program Officer
 JAMES A. TEW³, Accountant

1

Miss Ackerman, Dr. Davis, Mr. Haas, and Mr. Kempner were elected to the Council Board on November 2, 1974.

2

Mr. Butterfield succeeded Dr. Brooks on November 2, 1974.

3

Mrs. Hill resigned in June, 1975, and was replaced by Mr. Tew.

4

As of April, 1975.

5

Until his retirement March 31, 1975, when he became a consultant.

BOOKS AND ARTICLES RESULTING FROM COUNCIL GRANTS

Received July 1, 1974 - June 30, 1975

- * College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB), Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects. Program Summaries of the Participating Project Libraries. New York: CEEB, 1974. 16 pp. (CLR-557)
- * College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB), Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects. The Role of Public Libraries in Supporting Adult Independent Learning. An Interim Assessment. New York: CEEB, 1974. 68 pp. Appendices 82 pp.
- * Irvine, Betty Jo. Slide Libraries: A Guide for Academic Institutions and Museums. Littleton, Colorado: Libraries Unlimited, Inc., 1974. 212 pp. Bibliography, pp. 159-212. (CLR-519)
- * Sheridan, Robert N. "Measuring Book Disappearance." Library Journal, Vol. 99, No. 15 (September 1, 1974): 2040-2043. (CLR-497)
- * Gonzalez, Silvia. "Statistical Survey of Governmental Law Libraries." Law Library Journal, Vol. 66, No. 3 (August 1973): 290-310. (CLR-434)
- * Lewis, Alfred J. "1973 Statistical Survey of Law School Libraries and Librarians." Law Library Journal, Vol. 67, No. 2 (May 1974): 283-299. (CLR-434)
- * Gardner, Jeffrey J., and Webster, Duane E. The Formulation and Use of Goals and Objectives Statements in Academic and Research Libraries. Washington: Association of Research Libraries, Office of University Library Management Studies, August 1974. 45 pp. (CLR-555)
- * Overhage, Carl F. J., and Reintjes, J. Francis. "Project Intrex: A General Review." Reprinted from Information Storage & Retrieval, Vol. 10, Nos. 5/6, pp. 157-188. Oxford, England: Pergamon Press, 1974. (CLR-514)
- Gardner, Jeffrey J., Wax, David, and Morrison, R.D. Jr. "The Delivery of Computer-based Bibliographic Search Services by Academic and Research Libraries." ARL Management Supplement, Vol. 2, No. 2 (September 1974). (CLR-555)
- * Association of Research Libraries, Office of University Library Management Studies. "Collection Development in ARL Libraries." The Systems and Procedures Exchange Center Speed Flyer, No. 11 (September 1974). (CLR-555)
- W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. Physical and Chemical Properties of Book Papers, 1507-1949, Permanence/Durability of the Book series, Vol. VII. Richmond, Va.: W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., 1974. (CLR-594)
- * Sent to the Ford Foundation October 8, 1974

- Tsuneishe, Warren M., Buckman, Thomas, and Suzuki, Yukihiisa, eds. Issues in Library Administration, Papers Presented at the Second United States - Japan Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education, Racine, Wis., Oct. 17-20, 1972. New York: Columbia University Press, 1974. 181 pp. Japanese edition, 1974. (CLR-551)
- Hayes, Robert M., and Becker, Joseph. Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries, 2nd ed. Los Angeles: Melville Publishing Company, 1974. 688 pp. (CLR-312)
- USSR Cataloguing Committee. List of Uniform Headings for Higher Legislative and Ministerial Bodies in European Countries. London: IFLA Committee on Cataloguing, 1975. 41 pp. (CLR-584)
- Bolner, Mary, ed. Planning and Developing a Library Orientation Program, Proceedings of the Third Annual Conference on Library Orientation for Academic Libraries, Eastern Michigan University, May 3-4, 1973. Ann Arbor: Pierian Press, 1975. 72 pp. (CLR-598)
- Rader, Hannelore B., ed. Academic Library Instruction: Objectives, Programs, and Faculty Involvement, Papers of the Fourth Annual Conference on Library Orientation for Academic Libraries, Eastern Michigan University, May 9-11, 1974. Ann Arbor: Pierian Press, 1975. 84 pp. (CLR-598)
- Duckett, Kenneth W. Modern Manuscripts, A Practical Manual for Their Management, Care, and Use. Nashville: American Association for State and Local History, 1975. 473 pp. (CLR-480)
- Livingston, Lawrence G. "National Bibliographic Control: A Challenge." LC Information Bulletin, Vol. 33, No. 25 (June 21, 1974):A-108-113.(CLR-597)
- Anable, Richard. "CONSER: An Update." Journal of Library Automation, Vol. 8, No. 1 (March 1975): 26-30. (CLR-597)
- * Library of Congress. Cataloging in Publication Progress Report, Number 5. Washington: Library of Congress, July 1974. 16 pp. (CLR-522)

BOOKS AND ARTICLES RESULTING FROM CLR FELLOWSHIP GRANTS

- * Kronick, David A. "Studies of the Early Scientific Journal: I. The Basic Source Lists." Texas Reports on Biology and Medicine, Vol. 32, No. 1 (Spring 1974): 61-74.
- Smith, Jessie Carney. "Special Collection of Black Literature in the Traditionally Black College." College & Research Libraries, Vol. 35, No. 5 (September 1974): 322-335.
- Weatherford, John. "Collective Bargaining in Academe/Librarians in Faculty Unions." Library Journal, Vol. 99, No. 17 (October 1, 1974): 2243-6.
- _____. "Collective Bargaining in Academe/Professional Associations and Bargaining Agents." Library Journal, Vol. 100, No. 2 (January 15, 1975): 99-101.
- * Sent to the Ford Foundation October 8, 1974

- . "Participatory Something or Other Through Bargaining."
Library Journal, Vol. 100, No. 9 (May 1, 1975): 823-5.
- Lubans, John, Jr. Educating the Library User. New York: Bowker, 1974.
 435 pp.
- Fast, Elizabeth T. "In-Service Staff Development as a Logical Part of
 Performance Evaluation." School Media Quarterly, Vol. 3, No. 1
 (Fall 1974): 35-41.
- Dionne, Richard J. "Review of the Formulation and Use of Objectives in
 Academic and Research Libraries." ARL Management Supplement, Vol. 2,
 No. 1 (January 1974).
- Edwards, Fern. "Individual Access to Non Print Information for Deaf
 Students." Catholic Library World, September 1974: 68-71.
- Evans, G. Edward. "An American's View of Nordic Education Programs for
 Library Personnel." Scandinavian Public Library Quarterly, Vol. 7,
 No. 1 (1974): 2-15.
- Kenney, Brigitte L., ed. Cable Libraries, Vol. 2, No.1 (March 1974).
- Dain, Phyllis. "Ambivalence and Paradox: The Social Bonds of the Public
 Library." Library Journal, Vol. 100, No. 3 (February 1, 1975): 261-266.
- Johnson, Richard D. "Joint Academic Libraries." Advances in Librarianship,
 edited by Melvin J. Voigt, Vol. 5, pp. 321-354. New York: Academic
 Press, 1975.
- Dyson, Allan J. "Organizing Undergraduate Library Instruction: The
 English and American Experience." The Journal of Academic Librarianship,
 Vol. 1, No. 1 (March 1975): 9-13.
- Bone, Larry Earl. "The Public Library Goals and Objectives Movement:
 Death Gasp or Renaissance?" Library Journal, Vol. 100, No. 13 (July
 1975): 1283-86.
- LeClercq, Anne. "Organizing and Collecting Non-Print Materials in
 Academic Libraries." North Carolina Libraries, Vol. 1, No. 1 (Spring
 1975).

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

	Payable June 30, 1974	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1975
Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831					
Administration & Management Research Association of New York City, Inc. Creation of Citizens' Information Centers in the Brooklyn branches of the New York Public Library (544)	\$ 265,000		\$265,000		
American Association for State and Local History, Nashville, Tennessee Preparation of a book on the collection, care, and use of photographs (539)	8,300			\$ 2,800	\$ 5,500
Preparation of a manual on the collection and servicing of local history material in libraries (480)	6,430			3,750	2,680
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics, Washington, D. C. Statistical survey of law library resources in the U. S. and Canada (revised project) (434)	6,904			2,000	4,904
American Library Association, Chicago, Illinois Book catalog for a core collection for college libraries (462, 462/S)	91,912			91,912	
Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries (591)		\$ 8,372		4,000	4,372
<u>Revision of Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (ACCR) (610)</u>		111,431		50,000	61,431
The American Society for Information Science, Washington, D. C. Index to <u>JASIS</u> (Journal of the American Society for Information Science) (617)		19,910		10,000	9,910
Etta Arntzen, 109 Waverly Place, New York, New York Revision of <u>Guide to Art Reference Books</u> (510)	1,600				1,600
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D. C. Office of University Library Management Studies (613)		210,000			210,000
Support for ARL Office of University Library Management Studies (555, 555/S)	104,505			82,731	21,774
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., Richmond, Virginia* Operation of a laboratory for investigations relative to the preservation of books and other library materials (570, 594)	44,864	240,000	29,235	138,351	117,279

* Contract

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831	Payable June 30, 1974	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1975
Boston Theological Institute, Cambridge, Massachusetts ISSNs for theological serials (611)		\$ 1,000		\$ 750	\$ 250
Bucknell University, Lewisburg, Pennsylvania Automated on-line retrieval system (565)	\$ 5,250		\$ 2,827	3,250 (827)	
College Entrance Examination Board, New York, New York Support of the CEEB Office of Library Independent Study Projects (557, 557/S)				50,000	25,000
Columbia University, New York, New York Support for a planning office to be created within the Columbia University Library Structure (543)				26,800	9,508
Earlham College, Richmond, Indiana Periodical list for <u>Choice</u> magazine (608)				2,300	5,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Michigan Project LOEX: A Clearinghouse for Academic Libraries (598)				3,400	38,569
Division of Scientific and Technological Information and Documentation - UNISIST/FID/IFLA, Paris, France International summer school for teachers and workers in the information field (595)				2,200	
Dr. Hans-Peter Geh, Stuttgart, Germany Study tour of U. S. libraries (592)				2,129	
Governors State University, Park Forest South, Illinois Selective dissemination of microfiche documents in a university setting - pilot phase (561)				1,400	938
Graduate Library School, Indiana University, Bloomington, Indiana Analysis of library statistics (605)				972	
Dr. Milton O. Gustafson, Washington, D. C. Meeting of Association for Asian Studies (602)				270	
Margaret Hey, Istituto di Patologia del Libro, Rome, Italy Investigation of some book and archival paper restoration techniques (536)				209	
	493		284		

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831	Payable June 30, 1974	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1975
International Association of Law Libraries, Marburg/L., Germany To enable five law librarians from developing countries to attend the IALL's 5th International Course in Law Librarianship (587)	\$ 2,500			\$ 2,500	
International Council on Archives, Washington, D. C. Support of Secretariat of International Council on Archives (616)		\$ 72,000		5,500	\$ 66,500
International Federation for Documentation, c/o Robert Harte, Bethesda, Maryland Support for the FID Executive Committee Meeting, Washington, D. C., 11/18-20/74 (584)	1,680		\$ 960	1,680 (960)	
International Federation of Library Associations, Netherlands Congress Building, The Hague, Holland Establishment of a permanent Secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloging (515)	3,600			3,600	
Continued support for IFLA's Secretariat (578)	25,399	45,000		43,955	26,444
Universal Bibliographic Control (586, 615)	70,000	144,200		64,000	150,200
Stanford Junior University, Stanford, California Toward a California library automation network (CLAN) (609)		348,800		105,000	243,800
Library of Congress, Washington, D. C. Pilot project to test feasibility and utility of LC as a national bibliographic center (601-A)		94,632		27,000	67,632
Requirement study to determine hardware and software needs of a national bibliographic service (601-B)		6,500		5,000	1,500
National union catalog format study (601-C)		5,000		2,000	3,000
Equipment for Preservation Research Office (474)	25,000		25,000		
Dr. Donald M. Jacobs, Boston, Massachusetts Index of black newspapers published prior to the Civil War (603)		500		400	100
University of Iowa, Iowa City, Iowa Conference on "The Publication of American Historical Manuscripts" (604)		3,750		2,519	1,231

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

<u>Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831</u>	<u>Payable June 30, 1974</u>	<u>Grant Contract or Project</u>	<u>Adjust- ments</u>	<u>Payments (Refunds)</u>	<u>Payable June 30, 1975</u>
Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan Publication of a directory of university extension library services at NUEA and NASULGC member institutions (527)	\$ 402				\$ 402
R. Kathleen Molz, Washington, D. C. "Federal Policy and Library Planning," a book (593)		\$ 8,000		\$ 4,000	\$ 4,000
National Book Committee, Inc., New York City Partial support of a conference on the role of library services and educational materials in educational programs in developing countries (549)	2,500			2,500	
Conference to examine the effect of recent changes in public policy on the availability of books in the U. S. (564)	2,000		\$ 1,236	764	
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D. C. College library program (620)		100,000		100,000	
National serials data base in the humanities in machine-readable form (621)		118,600		118,600	
New England Interstate Library Compact, Hartford, Connecticut Support of New England Document Conservation Center (556)	31,800			31,800	
Ohio College Library Center, Columbus, Ohio Development of on-line acquisition subsystem (618)		124,250		45,000	79,250
Further development of OCLC's computerized regional library system (558)	24,000			24,000	
William S. Pierce, State College, Pennsylvania "Planning the Library Interior," a book (612)		3,000			3,000
Southeastern Library Network, Atlanta, Georgia Partial support of the program to train librarians to participate in the Southeastern Library Network (588)	10,000			6,600	3,400
Southwestern Library Association, Dallas, Texas Further development of the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE) (559)	26,800			26,800	
University of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois Library data management systems (606)		350,000		100,000	250,000

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831	Payable June 30, 1974	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1975
University of Chicago, Graduate Library School, Chicago, Ill. A Fellowship Program for the support of present holders of the Ph.D. degree as candidates for the M.A. degree in librarianship (568)	\$ 68,800			\$ 31,200	\$ 37,600
University of Lancaster, Lancaster, England Fundamental research on factors affecting the use of library service (505)	6,000		\$ 1,042	4,958	
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American National Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z39), Chapel Hill, N. C. Administration ANSI Committee Z39: library work, documentation and related publishing practices (575)	14,000	\$ 14,000		17,000	11,000
University of the State of New York, Albany, New York A study of State Government information needs (589)	25,000			21,000	4,000
Vanderbilt University on behalf of the Joint University Libraries, Nashville, Tennessee Establishment of a model research & development unit (473, 473/S)	109,010			53,250	55,760
Wabash College, Crawfordsville, Indiana To increase the effectiveness of the library in the educational program of Wabash College - College Library Program (486)	15,000			10,000	5,000
Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education, Boulder, Colorado Design and development of a western interstate bibliographic network, (614)				17,500	61,825
Council-Administered Projects: Advanced study program for librarians (619) Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control (607) Conversion of serials program (CONSER) (597) CLR Library Management Intern Program (579) Development and production of a simple microfiche reader testing device (566, 566/S)	94,114	115,000 22,000 250,000 265,000		305 2,259 24,274 115,553	114,695 19,741 225,726 243,561
	6,266	4,000		6,100	4,166

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS - YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc. One Dupont Circle, Suite 620 Washington, D. C. 20036 #53-0232831	Payable June 30, 1974	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments	Payable June 30, 1975
Feasibility study and initial pilot program leading to the development of a National Bibliographic Center (577)	\$ 44,232		\$ 21,553	\$ 22,679	
Fund for foreign librarians to visit the U. S. (471, 600)	1,765	\$ 3,500			\$ 5,265
Fund for foreign travel by U. S. librarians (542,576)	3,141			3,141	
Fund for foreign travel by U. S. Librarians (599)		5,000	81	2,194 (81)	2,806
Joint CLR-NSF Conference on National Bibliographic Control (580)	971			544	427
Academic Library Development Program (596)		100,000		11,875	88,125
Study of significant private research libraries in England, particularly in London (572)	8,105			2,255	5,850
Fellowship Program	96,652	72,823	19,596	63,823	88,056
TOTAL: GRANTS, CONTRACT, AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS	\$1,367,641	\$3,002,004	\$368,185	\$1,610,484	\$2,390,976
COMMITMENTS BY OTHERS FOR CO-SPONSORED PROJECTS					
National Commission on Libraries & Information Science (CLR 607)		5,000		513	4,487
National Science Foundation (CLR 607)		22,000		2,259	19,741
University of California at Berkeley (CLR-577)		2,000		2,000	
TOTALS	\$1,367,641	\$3,031,004	\$368,185	\$1,615,256	\$2,415,204